

BASIC CONCEPTS OF MULTIMEDIA SYSTEMS AND TECHNOLOGIES, FIELDS OF APPLICATION

Khairiyeva Shahnoza Saydulla kizi

Student

Navoi State Pedagogical Institute Faculty of Mathematics and Informatics

Abstract: This article presents suggestions and recommendations on ways to eliminate some shortcomings in the field of multimedia concept.

Key words: multimedia, information, technology, Internet, virtual.

Multimedia (multi copy, media environment) is a field of computer technologies that deals with information expressed in different physical forms in various information storage media.

Multimedia hardware and software tools allow the user to use useful audio and video file formats in addition to text and graphics, and create their own animated videos and films.

The concept of multimedia was formed in 1988 by the large European Commission dealing with the problems of implementation and use of new technologies.

At the end of the 80s of the 20th century, the interest in multimedia technologies is associated with the name of the famous American computer expert and businessman Bill Gates. He created a software product called "National Art Gallery London". This multimedia program uses the museum's archives. In it, the image, sound, animation, hypertext system from different environments are shown.

In this multimedia program that covers the three main principles of multimedia.

1. Representation of information using multiple mediums that can be perceived by a person.

2. Using independent methods based on independent search by the user, without going beyond the limits of the program.

3. Using navigation tools and interface design.

Multimedia technology: allows the simultaneous use of several methods of information presentation: text, graphics, animation, video and sound. The most important feature of multimedia technology is its ability to influence the user in the operation of an interactive information environment.

Multimedia tools: are a set of hardware and software tools that allow the user to communicate using sound, video, graphics, text, and animation.

It is possible to work with graphic and sound editors, personal application programs that can process cartographic information and texts. Such programs include programs such as Adobe PageMaker, Adobe Photoshop, Adobe Flash, 3D Max.

Multimedia presentation: is today the only and most modern form of information presentation. It can be textual information, pictures, slide show, voice-over, video clip and animation, three-dimensional graphic software. The main difference of the presentation from other forms of information presentation is their content enrichment and interactivity, that is, their tendency to change in the specified form and express the reaction to the user's activity.

A multimedia product: is an interactive, computer-generated product that can include streaming music, video clips, animation, picture and slide galleries, and various databases.

By virtual real system: we mean simulation software and hardware. To ensure interactivity, a virtual system the manager must accept the actions. These actions should be multimodal, i.e. visual and auditory. The concept of virtual reality was proposed by Jaron Lanier (Lane). Virtual reality is related to the concepts of immersiveness and interactivity. Immersiveness means that a person imagines himself in virtual reality. Interactivity allows the user to interact with virtual reality objects in real time and influence them.

Types of virtual entities:

1. passive virtual reality (passive virtual reality) is an autonomous graphic image that is not controlled by a person and is observed with sound;
2. the presence of a possibility to choose a script, image, sound provided to the user in a limited amount of the verified virtual entity;
3. interactive virtual entity is the ability of the user to control the virtual environment based on the laws of the world created with the help of a special device that can perform the tracking function;
4. tracking is designed to give the coordinates (x, y, z) of the location of the real object in the virtual environment and the angles of its location in space (a, b, g).

List of references:

1. Mo'minov B. B. Pedagogical software creation technology. Bukhara-2010.
2. Begimkulov U. Sh. Theoretical basis of introduction of modern information technologies in pedagogical education. Monograph. - T. Science. 2007. -160 p.
3. Kenjaboyev L.T. Problems of formation of national information system. -T. Ibn Sina, 2004. -251 p.
4. Lutfullayev M. Kh. Pedagogical software tools and their use in creating multimedia electronic textbooks. Public education. T, 2002. -No. 6. -p. 99-1